

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 727451

WP1	D1.3 MUSES Final Report
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MUSES Project

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Suggested Citation: Stephen J Sangiuliano, Susanne Altvater, Rebecca Bamlett, Andrea Barbanti, Martina Bocci, Bela H. Buck, Helena Calado, Mario Caña Varona, Sebastiano Carrer, Chiara Castellani, Daniel Depellegrin, Maximilian Felix Schupp, Ioannis Giannelos, Andronikos Kafas, Aneta Kovacheva, Gesche Krause, Zacharoula Kyriazi, Rianne Läkamp, Marija Lazić, Ivana Lukic, Athena Mourmouris, Joseph Onwona Ansong, Vincent Onyango, Eva Papaioannou, Joanna Przedzimirska, Emiliano Ramieri, Timothy Roberts, Angela Schultz-Zehden, Ilse van de Velde, Vassiliki Vassilopoulou, Chiara Venier, Marta Vergilio, Jacek Zaucha, Bruce Buchanan
Submission date: 31st October 2018

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Document Version Control			
Version	Date	Comment	Modified by
0.1	31/08/2018	Initial draft	SS
0.2	04/09/2018	Initial revisions	RB, BB, SS.
0.3	17/10/2018	Further updates and additional sections for final conference etc.	BB, TR
0.4	25/10/2018	Updates following comments from partners – split report into 2 separate formats: Executive Summary and Final Report	TR
1.0	31/10/2018	Finalisation and Upload to Portal	TR

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1. INTRODUCTION

The Multi-Use in European Seas (“MUSES”) project is a 2-year Horizon 2020 funded project under Grant Agreement No. 727451, consisting of a consortium of 10 project partners across seven different EU member states. The MUSES project builds on existing knowledge to explore the real opportunities for Multi-Use (“MU”) in Europe, including the scope for innovation and Blue Growth potential and to present practical solutions on how to overcome existing barriers and minimise risks associated with MU development. MUSES encompasses five EU sea basins (Baltic Sea, North Sea, Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea and Eastern Atlantic).

This Final Project Report provides an overview of European Sea Basins with respect to the potential and barriers to MU, a series of 10 case studies which explore the application of MU in practice, and an action plan to promote the implementation of MU and hence increase the Blue Growth economy. After the project is finished, the consortium will aim to build on the work carried out, and the recommendations produced by MUSES in order to maximise the long-term impact of the project.

The MUSES project was divided into six integrated Work Packages (“WPs”):

- WP1 – Project Management
- WP2 – Regional Sea Basin Overviews
- WP3 – Case Studies
- WP4 – Action Plan
- WP5 – Exploitation of Results
- WP6 – Ethics

The list of objectives for the MUSES project, as stipulated by the Grant Agreement, are as follows:

- Explore the opportunities for MU in European Seas, including the scope for innovation and Blue Growth potential. To be achieved by the review of past projects, initial desk research and initial interviews, to define which MUs combinations have an opportunity and should be explored further.
- Provide an understanding of environmental, spatial, economic & societal benefits of co-location
- Highlight inappropriate regulatory, operational, environmental, H&S, societal and legal aspects.
- Present practical solutions on how to overcome existing barriers and minimize risks associated with MU development whilst maximising local benefits

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2. METHODOLOGY

The MUSES project employed a unique methodology based on desk research and stakeholder engagement. The desk research portion of the project included an extensive literature review, including, but not limited to, government plans, protocols, policies, and legislation; industry assessments and consents; and academic papers from a variety of ecological, oceanographic, economic, engineering, and social themes. The information emanating from these documents was both validated and added to via extensive stakeholder engagement for various combinations, cases, and sea basins, totalling 195 stakeholder interviews, along with three stakeholder workshops.

MU, as defined within the MUSES project, is an **intentional joint use of resources in close geographic proximity**. It represents a radical change from the concept of exclusive resource rights to the inclusive sharing of resources by one or more uses.

An Analytical Framework (“AF”) was developed for analysing MU in these five European Sea Basins. The AF provides the project consortium with the practical research tools necessary to examine the theoretical understanding and practical experience related to MU. It is intended to guide the process of information and data gathering and stakeholder engagement of the five European Sea Basins. The flow chart below summarises the AF methodology. In simple terms the AF describes (1) Desk analysis; (2) Stakeholder Engagement and (3) Categories of MU factors – Drivers, Added values, Barriers & Impacts (“DABIs”).

Figure 1 – Graphical flow chart of the operational methodology and methods used for data collection and analysis. (Source: own elaboration by ISMAR)

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The sea basin analysis and case studies sought to identify and evaluate Drivers, Added Values, Barriers, and Impacts, along with MU Potential and MU Effect via a desk analysis which was valued and altered through stakeholder engagement. The definitions for these categories are provided below, with Figure 2 providing a graphic representation:

- DRIVERS = factors promoting MU - factors supporting / facilitating / strengthening MU development.
- ADDED VALUES = positive effects/impacts of establishing or strengthening MU - the positive effects of establishing / strengthening MU.
- BARRIERS = factors hindering MU - factors preventing /negatively affecting MU.
- IMPACTS (NEGATIVE IMPACTS) = negative effects of establishing / strengthening MU - the cons or the negative effects of implementing / strengthening MU.
- MU POTENTIAL is defined as the degree of opportunity the study area has to develop or strengthen MU.
- MU EFFECT is defined as the overall result or balance of pros and cons of developing MU in the study area.

Figure 2 – Diagram of the methodology for evaluating MU in Sea Basins and Case-Studies. (Source: own elaboration by THETIS)

There are also very close links with WP4. The WP4 Action plan will bring together the results generated by both WP2 and WP3 in a synthesis report to provide focus to the action plan.

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3. SEA BASIN FINAL REPORT (WP2)

The Sea Basin Final Report represents the culmination of the Regional Sea Basin Analysis for the MUSES project, with the findings contained therein directly influencing the final action plan and subsequent recommendation for the exploitation of results. Each interim Sea Basin report developed was informed by Country Fiches of nations adjacent to the basins. A total of 22 Country Fiches were produced and aggregated into each respective Sea Basin Interim Report.

The WP2 Final Report draws from all the preceding WP2 deliverables, collating and comparing information on the five sea basins and the identification of potential sectors and sea areas suitable for promotion of MU. The report was completed by the Maritime Institute in Gdansk (Poland) in coordination with MUSES project partners in April 2018.

The report details the steps which were undertaken in order to produce the final recommendations for the action plan. Work in WP2 focused on the examination of the theoretical understanding and practical experience of MU in European Seas. The work comprised of the following steps: (i) identification of MUs (the type of combinations and where geographically they occur), (ii) identification of the most important real and perceived barriers and drivers as well as impacts and added values of these MUs, and (iii) depiction of similarities and differences through comparative analysis of MU specificities in various EU seas and oceans.

Table 1 – MUs selected as the most relevant in the sea basins analysis

No	MU Name	EA	NS	BSR	MED	BS
1	Offshore Wind & Aquaculture	3	4	4	2	
2	Offshore Wind & Tourism	2	1	5		
3	Offshore Wind & Fisheries	1	4	1		
4	Aquaculture & Tourism	4		1	6	2
5	Fisheries & Tourism & Environmental Protection	3		1	8	2
6	Underwater Cultural Heritage & Tourism & Environmental Protection	3		6	5	2
7	Tidal & Wave	1	1			
8	Offshore Wind & Wave	2	1			

Following the presentation of all the MU combinations analysed in each of the five sea basins, a discussion of the top prioritized MU combinations (Table 1), and an overview of stakeholder perceptions, the WP2 Final Report puts forth four distinct sets of recommendations:

MUSES Project Methodology

- It has allowed for the identification of the most important MUs at the sea basin level together with their key drivers and barriers

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- The most important advantage of this methodology was its focus on stakeholder engagement. This in turn has allowed for the realistic verification of the findings retrieved either from desk research and/or in the course of in-depth interviews.
- Thanks to all these, the project was able to deliver meaningful policy relevant conclusions.

Drivers & Barriers

1. To be successful, MU deployment requires as a minimum two out of three players willing to establish MU: either both sectors or one sector and the regulator.
2. There are three sectors that can be considered as MU drivers: tourism, offshore wind energy and environmental protection.
3. It is important to differentiate between soft (a non-physical link between two activities) and hard (implying physical connection between two (or more) installations) MUs. The soft and hard MUs are characterised by different dynamics and they should therefore be analysed separately.
4. Each sea basin has its peculiarities concerning MU implementation. The tourism sector is a major driver in southern Europe, while the wind energy sector is considered as having potential in the north and western part.
5. Some countries have particularly advanced MU implementation within certain combinations. This is relevant for existing but also for planned MUs.
6. Public support to MU development should take into consideration the above findings.
7. The forms of public support should be adjusted to the stage of maturity of a given MU.
8. Drivers differ among MU combinations. However, for all combinations there is a need to strengthen relevant EU policies and EU macro-regional strategies in their role as MU supporters and promoters.
9. Equally important is to put some effort into MU outreach. This will allow the reinforcement of the existing drivers with the perceived drivers that in general are lagging behind.
10. For combinations related to tourism, the economic drivers seem sufficient. For other combinations, the MU deployment would require dedicated financial incentives.
11. In order to identify possible progress in the development of a given MU, not only peculiarities of sea basins and countries should be considered.
12. However, it would be wise to differentiate such type of actions. For MUs with few barriers (e.g. those related to tourism), perhaps focus should be on the reinforcement of drivers. For other MUs, both barriers and drivers should be addressed.
13. There is a need to support not only technological readiness but also proper programming for MU dedicated to wind energy and aquaculture.
14. There is a need to reconsider administrative procedures in order to smooth MU deployment (unified licencing and permitting processes)
15. The policy support related to Fisheries and Tourism and Environmental Protection can be focused on dissemination of good practices, transfer of know-how and reduced administrative barriers
16. The support must be adjusted to macro-regional needs and specificity.
17. MSP seems to play an important role as a driver for many MUs. It goes without saying that the MU concept should be supported under MSP.

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18. The potential added values of MUs (recognised by all groups/categories of stakeholders) cannot be proved without well-thought-out and properly programmed field experiments involving both sectors and regulators.
19. Only based on the above proposed field experiments, the impacts of MU can be properly and subjectively addressed.

Stakeholder Perceptions Related of MU & Related Drivers & Barriers

- Stakeholders representing single uses were the most important knowledge sources for the MU combinations in relation with the OW and aquaculture.
- Representatives of the MUs in combination with environmental protection and UCH were mostly cross-sector stakeholders.
- Representatives of the sea basins differ from the level of development of the MU or single sector (i.e. distribution of representatives and involved stakeholders from the OW sector from Northern European seas was higher than in the Mediterranean Sea).
- An effective mechanism to identify and enforce existing regulations supporting MU combinations is needed.
- Support from regulators from different scales (international, EU, regional sea and national) is expected including promotion of the MU concept benefits.
- A stakeholder engagement and MU awareness strategy must be established to properly deal with the social and authority acceptance of the concept.
- Stakeholders should be given the opportunity to obtain knowledge and understanding of the MU

Future Research on MU Development

- Interplay between single uses and genuine MU barriers
- Differences between hard and soft MUs
- Governance delivery in terms of MU (e.g. why the UK government delivers on MU and other governments do not as much)
- MU incentives (economic, legal, societal initiatives supporting MU),
- Role of MU in fostering economies of agglomeration,
- Impact of MU on sea-land interactions,
- MU cumulative economic, social and environmental impacts,
- Inclusion of MU under sectoral policies (not only under MSP)
- Pilot testing of the policies, incentives and governance patterns suitable for MU.

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4. CASE STUDIES (WP3)

WP3 considers and analyses MU through a comprehensive set of case studies of real and/or potential MU to provide a complete spectrum of advantages in combining different uses of the sea. Based on extensive desk research, the case studies will engage stakeholders in identifying MU potentiality, opportunities and limitations.

A total of 10 distinct case studies were considered across European seas. These case studies are illustrated as numbered orange circles at Figure 3. The case study level analysis considered future MU potentials on the basis of:

- existing legal, policy, strategic and planning documents covering MU at case study level
- the literature findings and the experience of the completed and on-going international projects
- stakeholder involvement
- other available information.

Figure 3 – MUSES Case Studies

The 10 reports drew from the report Case Study Methodology and Stakeholder Identification & Engagement. Along with identifying and evaluating DABI, the case studies consisted of a Focus Area Analysis, whereby a list of Key Evaluation Questions standard across all cases were categorised (and answered by stakeholders) under the themes of:

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- i. Addressing MU
- ii. Boosting Blue Growth Potential, and
- iii. Improving Environmental Compatibility (Figure 5)

FA1: Addressing-MU **FA2: Boosting Blue-Growth potential** **FA3: Improving environmental compatibility**

	FA1	FA2	FA3
Case-Study 1			
Case-Study 2			
Case-Study 3	FA1 Key Evaluation Questions	FA2 Key Evaluation Questions	FA3 Key Evaluation Questions
Case-Study 4			
Case-Study 5			
Case-Study 6			
Case-Study 7			

Figure 5 - Focus Area Analysis

The 10 cases which were aggregated to develop the Case Study Implementation were as follows:

- Case study 1A - Multi-use space between commercial fisheries and offshore wind farms in Scotland (East Coast of Scotland - North Sea)
- Case study 1B - Tidal energy development and environmental protection and monitoring (North Coast of Scotland - Inner sound of the Pentland Firth - North Sea)
- Case study 1C - Multi-use of off-shore wind farms with marine aquaculture and fisheries (German North Sea EEZ - North Sea)
- Case study 2 - Marine Renewables & Aquaculture Multi-use including the use of marine renewable energy near the point of generation (West Coast of Scotland - Northern Atlantic Sea)
- Case study 3A - Development of tourism and fishing in the Southern Atlantic Sea (South Coast of mainland Portugal - Algarve region - Atlantic Sea)
- Case study 3B - Development of tourism and fishing in the Southern Atlantic Sea (Azores archipelago – Eastern Atlantic Sea)
- Case study 4 - Multi-Use for local development focused on energy production, tourism and environment in Swedish waters (Island of Gotland - Baltic Sea)
- Case study 5 - Offshore wind and mariculture: potentials for multi-use and nutrient remediation in Rødsand 2 (South Coast of Lolland-Falster - Denmark - Baltic Sea)
- Case study 6 - Coastal & Maritime Tourism and O&G Decommissioning as drivers for potential Multi-use in the Northern Adriatic Sea (Italy - Mediterranean Sea)
- Case Study 7 - Marine Renewable Energy Sources & Desalination, Fishing & Tourism in the South Aegean: the case of Mykonos Island (Greece - Mediterranean Sea).

The Case Study Comparative Analysis Final Report represents the culmination of the WP3 Case Studies Within EU Sea Basins Analysis for the MUSES project, with the findings

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contained therein directly influencing the final Action Plan and subsequent recommendations for the exploitation of results. The Case Study Comparative Analysis Report draws from all the preceding WP3 deliverables, synthesizing the analysis of MU opportunities and operation in each of the case studies and the results of crosscutting analysis. The report was completed by Thetis SPA (Italy) in coordination with MUSES project partners in April 2018.

The 10 case studies identified and evaluated sixteen MU combinations in total. A high degree of heterogeneity and local specificity in terms of combinations considered is shown across the cases, with 11 combinations being considered by single cases and only five combinations are relevant for more than one case. These five combinations were analysed in more detail in the report and are as follows:

1. Tourism & Fisheries
2. Wind energy & Aquaculture
3. Tourism & Environmental protection
4. Wind energy & Fisheries
5. Tourism & Aquaculture.

The Case Study Comparative Analysis Report concluded with the following recommendations aimed towards the Action Plan:

1. **MSP process** at national and sub-national levels can support MU development including explicit reference/policies towards MU, assisting in the identification of areas suitable for establishing MU combinations, addressing actions aimed at removing barriers to MU, targeting cross-sector needs and opportunities, and encouraging a shift from a sectoral approach to a MU opportunity planning approach.
2. MU development would benefit from **national/sub-national legal frameworks for MU**. MU can be promoted through licensing processes and by introducing it in EIA processes. Improving coherence of legislation and administrative procedures across sectors (at least) at the national level would also be a key factor for MU development. Ensuring harmonization of local and sub-national administrative procedures is required too.
3. **Focussing and targeting of existing EU regional funds on MU is essential**. They should target MU implementation including development of concrete business cases, valorisation, promotion of operators' skills enhancement, etc. Moreover, it is key to sustain MU implementation over time (through funding), after the pilot phase.
4. The explored combinations with offshore wind energy would benefit from **additional research** on environmental compatibility, on new opportunities emerging from combining uses, on risk assessment and prevention (e.g. navigational hazards), and pilot project development. The development of the tourism-related combinations seems to be less dependent on additional research, though better knowledge on the bio-economy chain and socio-economic aspects would undoubtedly be beneficial to boost these MUs.
5. **Development of pilot cases** is indicated as beneficial for the considered combinations with offshore wind energy production. In the case of the explored combinations with

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tourism, successful experiences and transfer of good practices are considered as motivators (drivers) for additional MU implementation.

6. **Strengthening of dialogue and cooperation** is recommended for all the combinations explored in this chapter. Different actors to be involved in dialogue (economic sectors, governmental institutions, society at large) and different vertical and horizontal dimensions for the dialogue are emphasised. Physical meetings and all occasions for joint discussion and project development are also recommended to facilitate MU implementation.
7. **Education and training**. Improve skills of sector operators (e.g. fisheries, aquaculture) through targeted educational programs would benefit MU by providing a better understating of its opportunities. Training and capacity-building for MU and other basic educational actions are also recommended, e.g. foreign languages and entrepreneurship in the case of tourism related MU and business skills (e.g. contractors) in the case of wind related MU.
8. **Communication and social awareness** are seen as a common need for all the examined combinations. The general public and local communities should be informed about the opportunities offered by MU. Promotion of MU benefits to the society at large would be beneficial for the implementation of all the combinations related with tourism. Participatory processes and links of MU to Corporate Social Responsibility should be encouraged. Communication on MU could also be done through the social media and can include facilitation to access to specific data (e.g. location of environmental and UCH sites open to visitors).

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5. ACTION PLAN (WP4)

Deliverables under WP4 included an Overview of Stakeholder Profiles, a Sea Basin Synthesis, and concluding with the Action Plan, which proposes actions and recommendations to address the challenges and opportunities for the development of MU's of seas identified in the regional overviews and case studies.

The overall aim of the stakeholder analysis is to gain a better understanding of the various actors relevant in the context of MU combinations examined in the MUSES project. Therefore, taking into consideration different geographical scales, the stakeholder profiles was developed with specific attention to those actors identified to be behind the drivers and barriers for the MU development in question. Stakeholder analysis is an iterative process that will evolve throughout the stages of the MUSES project, rather than a one-off isolated analytical step. Stakeholder analysis was conducted in parallel with barrier/driver identification and evaluation. As new information was gained (purposefully or opportunistically) during the course of the project, stakeholder information was updated and revised, with an intention to deepen the analysis. This informed the development of the Action Plan which targeted the right type of stakeholders with the right type of action, considering national, regional and sea basin dimensions. Specifically, the Action Plan highlights the real opportunities for MUs in European Seas including the scope for innovation and Blue Growth potential, and propose solutions to overcome existing barriers.

Following the consideration of MU combinations for themes and categories, elaboration on the six following attributes were made based on desk analysis and stakeholder engagement activities:

- Overall interest in MU
- Overall attitude towards MU
- Geographical scale at which certain stakeholder has the power
- Organisation of stakeholder and sea basin stakeholder network
- Type of power
- Level of power.

Using this methodology, stakeholder profiles were elaborated for each stakeholder theme relevant to each country and each stakeholder category under each theme as specified above. The information on stakeholder attributes collected through desk research and interviews was recorded in the excel sheet to form a database for the analysis necessary for stakeholder visualisation diagrams. Information from the country inputs for each of the MU combinations was synthesized to sea basin overview including the visual presentation through Venn diagrams in preparation for the Force Field analysis.

The Overview of MU Analysis Report was completed in April 2018. The report analyses the findings of WP2 and WP3, as well as the various MUSES workshops held throughout the project up to the deliverable date, in order to provide a clear overview of 13 selected MU in European Sea basins, with an emphasis on the identification of real and perceived barriers to implementation of MU.

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The Overview of MU Analysis Report presents findings concerning a sea basin comparison (Figure 6), concluding with the following highlights:

- The EU sea basins offer variety of MU opportunities depending on physical and environmental conditions and available resource;
- The MU combinations that concern the diversification of tourism and fishing sector in combination with sustainability and environmental protection goals are relevant in the Mediterranean, the Black Sea and the coastal areas of the Eastern Atlantic;
- Underwater Cultural Heritage MU combinations have strong potential in the Mediterranean and Baltic Sea and other environmental/conservation benefits of this MU have been realised;
- The North Sea and specific areas of the Mediterranean Sea (Northern Adriatic in particular) have the potential for development of innovative solutions for sustainable reuse of decommissioned O&G platforms;
- The North Sea, Eastern Atlantic and the Baltic Sea have a strong offshore wind energy sector that could potentially develop further while also allowing growth in other relevant Blue Growth sectors such as tourism, fishing and aquaculture;
- Offshore wave energy can be combined with other energy sectors so that all energy sources at the given area are utilised. Or, it can be combined with aquaculture to support its operations.

Figure 6 - Analysed MU combinations across five European sea basins.

The report also targets the actors relevant for the strengthening and development of MU. The MUSES project had conducted 195 interviews with relevant actors, from the Mediterranean Sea (53), Baltic Sea (48), North Sea (38), Eastern Atlantic (37), Black Sea (19), in order to acquire perspectives on various relevant MU combinations from all sea basins.

The Sea Basin Synthesis report was completed in August 2018 (Figure 7). The report identifies potential for MU applications across the five European sea basins, depicting MU applications with real potential and where, and maps the opportunities and actions to promote MU

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implementation. The Sea Basin Synthesis underpins the development of the final MUSES Action Plan.

For each of the five sea basins (with the exception of the black Sea), the report details (a) an overview of opportunities, (b) an overview of main barriers, (c) the case studies undertaken in the sea basin, (d) the actors, and (e) a list of recommendations. A summary of these contents for each sea basin are presented in the subsections below. (Note: the Black Sea only contains overviews of opportunities and barriers and MU policy overview).

Figure 7 – MU image developed during the Venice Stakeholder Workshop

The Action Plan builds on the work undertaken at the Sea Basin (WP2) and Case Study (WP3), level drawing on the expertise of many stakeholders as summarised below:

195
INTERVIEWS
+
2 WORKSHOPS
IN **5** EU SEA BASINS
+
1 WORKSHOP
IN THE NORTH SEA

117
INTERVIEWS
+
1 FOCUS GROUP
+
1 WORKSHOP
IN **10** MUSES CASE
STUDY LOCATIONS

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The **Final Action Plan** consists of the following parts:

Part 1 - introduces the MU concept, its policy background and the MUSES methodology. It summarises its stage of development, possible benefits of and opportunities for MU, as well as what kind of support the MU concept receives across Europe.

MU, as defined within the MUSES project, is an **intentional joint use of resources in close geographic proximity**. It represents a radical change from the concept of exclusive resource rights to the inclusive sharing of resources by one or more uses.

Part 2 - specifies the actions required for each of the nine MU combinations across Europe deemed “most important” by the MUSES Project. It commences with tourism-related MUs which are largely based on operational synergies, before going on to discuss energy-related MUs which often entail a higher level of physical integration. For each combination, we explain what the MU entails and its current state of development, and summarise its associated positive drivers/benefits as well as negative barriers/impacts. Most significantly, we then conclude with the key recommendations which need to be considered to advance each MU. Where possible, we indicate where the action is needed, who should be responsible for implementing it and whether it should be pursued at local, national, sea-basin or wider European level.

The nine MU combinations, which were found to be of highest relevance across Europe were:

1. Tourism, fisheries & environmental protection
2. Tourism, underwater cultural heritage & environmental protection
3. Tourism and aquaculture
4. Offshore wind farm and tourism
5. Offshore wind farm and fisheries
6. Offshore wind farm and aquaculture
7. Oil and Gas and Decommissioning – Repurposing
8. Offshore wave energy and aquaculture
9. Offshore wind and marine renewable energy

Part 3 - presents the overarching conclusions and recommendations across all MU combinations. This is particularly advantageous as some actions are not specific to one combination only and require action by the same specific actors and regulators.

7.6.1. Action Plan - Overarching Conclusions & Recommendations in brief

INTEGRATION & COORDINATION

MU as a concept is still novel for government authorities, sectoral bodies and policy makers. These actors must adjust policy, planning, consenting and management reform in order to advance synergies between maritime uses that are usually managed under different sectoral institutions and owners. Integration and coordination at vertical (across levels of governance) and horizontal levels (across sectors and policy topics) is needed. This may be achieved by

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setting up cross-sectoral platforms to guide the development of MU, involving continuous stakeholder engagement, exchange of knowledge and integration of new MU actors.

MARITIME SPATIAL PLANNING

MSP supports an integrated approach to and efficient use of maritime space. Current MSP processes offer an opportunity for planning authorities, together with stakeholders, to identify suitable areas and comprehensive policies promoting MU, especially for new joint developments. Moreover, data generated throughout the process should be shared with stakeholders to promote possible opportunities for MU development.

POLICY & REGULATION

MU development may flourish under clear direction and comprehensive national legal frameworks which specify safety, insurance and permitting process standards. Clear direction and guidelines from the EU and the responsible directorates are needed for integrating operational issues about MU into EU and national policies. For example, pescatourism will need a clear definition on which activities are involved, which taxation regime can be applied and indication of how Member States can adapt their institutions and regulations for its implementation.

CAPACITY BUILDING

MU actors involved in developing MUs at the project and operational level such as ocean users, investors and businesses have different capacity building needs such as know-how, training, finance, logistics and public awareness that needs to be addressed to ensure the success of a MU venture. Responsible sub-national and national authorities should support these actors through comprehensive training, providing financial support and encouraging professional and personal networks between stakeholders at regional, national and international levels.

PROMOTION & DISSEMINATION

Promoting good practices and disseminating information about the economic and societal benefits of MUs through existing regional and sea basin forums and networks is necessary to facilitate its replication and encourage investment. Such promotional support should consider the needs of actors at the local level to ensure that their issues and values are addressed. MU projects and business cases should put more focus on developing marketing strategies to increase the awareness and value of their products and services.

FUNDING

The success of MU implementation mainly depends on an in-depth understanding of its appeal to stakeholders and its readiness for the target market. Targeted incentives for MU are needed to advance its implementation, while existing funding schemes directed towards single sectors should be adapted to consider MU. Funding should also support those small scale or local MU solutions that may not have a high contribution to the national GDP, but may render important socio-economic and cultural benefits for the local communities, as well as wider environmental benefits. However, for the long-term financial viability of MU, there is a need for development of new financial instruments, business models and for monetisation of possible services and products along the full value chain of the MU.

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RESEARCH PRIORITIES

Research for MU is needed, not only for technological development, but to understand the economic, social, and environmental impacts of MU, along with related legal aspects such as liability and insurance issues. Identifying research areas and undertaking pilots in the real environment led by research centres would allow the development of full-scale business models; enhance understanding of the MU value chain and the opportunities that it presents; and generate recommendations for advancing MU.